

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8217555>

GU JOURNAL OF PHYTOSCIENCES

GU. J. Phytosci. 3(3): 196-203 (2023)

Spatio-Temporal Differences in The Water Quality of Nullah Palkhu on Various Locations of Districts Sialkot & Gujranwala, Pakistan

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Abstract

Spatial and temporal changes in the water value of Nullah Palkhu were studied from June (Pre-Monsoon) to September (post-Monsoon) 2017. The samples were analysed for total dissolved solids, electrical conductivity, pH, turbidity, chlorine, total hardness, nitrate, salinity, calcium, magnesium, biological oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, dissolved oxygen, iron, lead, and cadmium. The tests were performed in the research laboratory of the Pakistan Council for Research in Water Resources. Most parameters were above the acceptable limit. The Spatio-Temporal variations were evident from the fact that the results of samples collected from upstream locations had lesser contamination as compared with the samples collected from downstream locations. It indicated that industrial, domestic and agricultural, etc. wastes were dumped into the lower stream segments, which play a key role in contamination. The results indicate the necessary control of human actions in the catchment of Nullah Palkhu and highlight the significance of restoration.

Keywords: Gujranwala; Nullah Palkhu; Sialkot; Spatio-Temporal Variations; Water Contaminants; Water Quality

1. Introduction:

Water is a key requirement to put up with life. However, it has both quantitative and qualitative limitations. Inhabitants of a specific place can face water scarcity and health-associated dangers from drinking polluted water. Freshwater resources and population density are unequally distributed, putting a strain on the availability of safe water for many people around the world (Nazir *et al.*, 2011; Shah *et al.*, 2019;

Islam *et al.*, 2020).

Individuals living in dry and semiarid areas of the biosphere always search for the availability of safe drinking water. This freshwater deficiency is multiplied many times due to the pollution of freshwater assets by different types of contaminants, which has the potential to decrease the quality of water day by day (Qu *et al.*, 2008; Khan *et al.*, 2020).

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© 2023 (Accepted for publication in April 2023)

Published by Department of Botany, Selection and/or peer-review under supervision of Executive Committee, Ghazi University, DG Khan, 32200 Pakistan

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Human activities degrade the water value in streams and tributaries (Singh *et al.*, 2005a; Shrestha & Kazama, 2007; Qadir *et al.*, 2008) and put them at risk (Gafny *et al.*, 2000; Korfali & Davis, 2003; Singh *et al.*, 2007). Rash growth in cities and manufacturing development has increased the process of degradation (Ghosh & McBean, 1998). Manufacturing and crop-growing fields are also sources of organic contaminants in fresh water (Honnen *et al.*, 2001; Singh *et al.*, 2005a; Gallo *et al.*, 2006; Siddique *et al.*, 2021).

Usually, surface water contains a dissolved or suspended particulate phase (Saeedi *et al.*, 2004; Gallo *et al.*, 2006; Siddique *et al.*, 2021). Liquefied forms make the environment fragile because contaminants can gather in aquatic organisms. Organic matter and inorganic compounds both contribute significantly to the spread of contaminants (Lee *et al.*, 2003; Gallo *et al.*, 2006; Rothwell *et al.*, 2006; Singh *et al.*, 2005b). Changes in many metals in tributaries are extremely variable and controlled by various methods. These methods include watercourse release, natural processes, and human actions (Simeonov, 2003; Khan *et al.*, 2020). Time-based changes are controlled by stream release level and rainfall (Singh *et al.*, 2004; Singh *et al.*, 2005a; Shah *et al.*, 2007; Islam *et al.*, 2020). Streams and tributaries in South Asia are facing different cyclical rainfalls. The pollution of water bodies in South Asia has been reported by various workers. Viz., Singh *et al.* (2005a) emphasised the spatio-temporal changes and water quality of the Gomti River, a tributary of the Ganga in India. Chakrapani (2005) describes the spatial and temporal changes in the amounts of major and trace elements in the Ganga river water in India. Qadir *et al.* (2008) reported the effects of human actions on the spatio-temporal variations of the Aik, a tributary of the Chenab River in Pakistan, and so on.

One of the main streams of the River Chenab is Nullah Palkhu, which continuously receives manufacturing and public wastes from the region of Sialkot. Due to the dreadful conditions of the water environment, raw wastes are pushing water assets

toward hazards and a major danger (Qadir *et al.*, 2008). No related research is present on Nullah Palkhu, and it is required to describe the significance of upcoming threats based on full calculation to discover the temporal and spatial changes in water value. A complete observing method was planned to acquire reliable temporal and spatial information for upcoming reinstatement. The study had two objectives, the first was to measure the spatial and temporal variations of wastes, and the second was to classify the causes of contamination in Nullah Palkhu.

1.1. Objectives:

- To measure the spatial and temporal variations of wastes, and the second was to classify the causes of contamination in Nullah Palkhu.
- To enumerate and classify the causal factors of contamination in Nullah Palkhu.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Study Area:

Current research was focused on Nullah Palkhu (32° 24' to 32° 37' N & 73° 59' to 75° 02'E) of Districts Sialkot & Gujranwala, Pakistan. The Nullah Palkhu is a tributary of the Chenab that begins its journey in Jammu at an elevation of 860 feet above sea level and travels 99.5 km with an average release of 440 C and cleanliness of approximately 962 km². The regular yearly rainfall in the area is ~ 950mm.

Nullah Palkhu is contaminated by both point and nonpoint sources. Point causes gather waste from Sambrial, Sialkot, and Wazirabad. Non-point sources are fertilizers and pesticides added to the stream environment through heavy rain. The release varies significantly, with contributions from various areas increasing. This contaminated water is also used to water cropland along the tributaries.

2.2. Global positioning system (GPS) locations of different sites of Nullah Palkhu:

Table 1. GPS locations of different sites of Nullah Palkhu

Sampling Sites	GPS Locations
P1 (Bridge near colony, Sialkot)	32° 32' 11" N 74° 32' 47" E
P2 (Airport, Sialkot)	32° 30' 56" N 74° 22' 24" E
P3 (KotKhudayar)	32° 27' 58" N 74° 13' 31" E
P4 (Wazirabad Bridge)	32° 27' 07" N 74° 07' 17" E
P5 (Wazirabad city)	74° 07' 08" E 32° 27' 06" W

The testing was begun at an early hour of the day, ranging from 7:00 a.m. to 3:00 p.m. Three sub-tests were gathered from every site. Water tests were gathered on regular premises from June to September 2017. Water testing was done from June (Pre-Monsoon) to September (post-Monsoon) 2017. Description of each site is given in table 1.

2.3. Water Sampling and Laboratory Analysis:

Water samples were collected in disinfected glass water sampling bottles that were tightly sealed. Samples were collected 20 cm below the surface of the water and within 100 meters of the examination site. To avoid air bubbles, sampling containers were carefully placed in examining bottles. From each site, three sub-tests of stream water were collected, which were then joined to get composite samples for analysis.

The water samples were kept in plastic containers and were firmly fixed to avoid spillage during transportation. All water tests were kept in refrigerators and transported to the research Centre as

suggested by the endorsed standard strategy (APHA, 1998). All samples were transported to the lab of the Pakistan Council of Research in Water Resources (PCRWR), Lahore. All examinations on water were performed in the PCRWR research facility. Water samples were fixed with a few drops of nitric acid for analysis metal ion concentration. Total dissolved solids (TDS), electrical conductivity (EC), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, and salinity were examined on site. Whereas hardness, turbidity, chemical oxygen demand (COD), NO₃⁻, Ca, Cl, Cd, Mg, Fe, and Pb were examined in the lab. The biological oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) were calculated by standard procedures.

2.4. Statistical Analysis:

The means, medians, standard errors, and standard deviations were measured. IBM-SPSS version 20 statistics were used to calculate one-way ANOVA, and Microsoft Excel 2010 was used for graphical representation (Microsoft Corporation, 1985).

Table 2: One-way ANOVA indicates the Signiant co-relation between different values

Parameters	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom	Mean Square	F Value	P Value
TDS	63680.4	1	63680.4	2.7	.1 ns
	184427.2	8	23053.4		
	248107.6	9			
EC	689062.5	1	689062.5	6.399	.03*
	861522.4	8	107690.3		
	1550584.9	9			
pH	.049	1	.049	.456	.5 ns
	.8	8	.107		
	.9	9			
Turbidity	6350.4	1	6350.4	3.585	.09 ns
	14172.0	8	1771.5		
	20522.4	9			
Cl	5569.6	1	5569.6	7.06	.02*
	6304.8	8	788.1		
	11874.4	9			
Total Hardness	15132.1	1	15132.1	9.6	.01*
	12552.0	8	1569.0		
	27684.1	9			
NO3	.182	1	.182	2.2	.1 ns
	.653	8	.082		
	.835	9			
Ca	115.6	1	115.6	3.22	.1 ns
	286.4	8	35.8		
	402.0	9			
Mg	336.4	Es1	336.4	2.93	.1 ns
	916.0	8	114.5		
	1252.4	9			
Salinity	.008	1	.008	.403	.5 ns
	.167	8	.021		
	.175	9			
BOD	7507.6	1	7507.6	2.992	.1 ns
	20076.0	8	2509.5		

COD	27583.6	9			
	230.4	1	230.4	.664	.4 ns
	2775.2	8	346.9		
DO	3005.6	9			
	2.9	1	2.916	1.27	.2 ns
	18.3	8	2.294		
Fe	21.2	9			
	.024	1	.024	.473	.5 ns
	.406	8	.051		
Pb	.430	9			
	.011	1	.011	.256	.6 ns
	.340	8	.042		
Cd	.351	9			
	.000	1	.0	1.220	.3 ns
	.002	8	.0		
	.002	9			

Figure 1: Spatio-temporal variations in the water quality of nullah Palkhu A: Total Dissolved Solids, B: Electrical conductivity, C: pH, D: Turbidity, E: Chloride; F: Total hardness, G: Nitrates, H: Calcium (R1: First reading, R2: Second reading, P1: First site of nullah Palkhu, P2: Second site, P3: Third site, P4: Forth site, P5: Fifth site)

Figure 2: Spatio-temporal variations in the water quality of nullah Palkhu A: Magnesium, B: salinity, C: Biological Oxygen Demand, D: Chemical Oxygen Demand, E: Lead, F: Cadmium, G: Dissolved Oxygen, H: Iron (R1: First reading, R2: Second reading, P1: First site of nullah Palkhu, P2: Second site, P3: Third site, P4: Forth site, P5: Fifth site)

3. Results:

Pre-monsoon samples were designated as R1 whereas post-monsoon samples were labelled as R2. The results from the present study indicate that the mean values of TDS, EC, pH, turbidity, Cl, total hardness, NO₃, salinity, Cl, Mg, BOD, COD, DO, Fe, Pb and Cd had higher mean values in R1 samples, collected during the month of June (pre-monsoon), as compared to R2 samples which were collected during the month of September (post-monsoon). This is because during the month of June there was less rain thereby the contaminants had higher concentrations. During the month of September there was higher flooding of Nullah due to monsoon rains. The contaminants were therefore found in relatively diluted form. This indicated significant temporal

variations of contaminants in Nullah Palkhu.

Regular contrasts in grouping of contaminants might be because of variance in the stream release level. Amid storm season, because of high release level the impact of waste weakened while in winter and late-spring, streams encounter extraordinarily low release level. The measure of waste issues stays same during the time in the catchment zone and contaminants fixation is normally greater near to the ground stream.

It was also found that the TDS and EC calculated before monsoon were higher than that of after monsoon. This is possibly because the Nullah Palkhu densely populated industrial areas of Sialkot as compared to Nullah Halsi.

The presence of salinity, turbidity and hardness in water highly influences the accessibility of metals. At higher concentration of salinity in water,

ionic metals react with partially dissolved particulate metals and become insoluble and settle down in residue. Tributary release level reduces the concentration of salt in tributary water. Therefore, the variations in saltiness can be related with high concentration of dissolvable salts utilized. Mg and Ca are the main deciding elements that contribute to hardness in freshwater, different factors additionally contribute to an expansion in absolute firmness.

Nullah Palkhu can be characterize as hard water while tributary water after rainstorm and before storm season. The outcomes demonstrated that most extreme aggregate firmness was recorded in winter while the tributary turn out to be near to the ground and wastes originating from tanneries encased greater centralization of calcium salts release into tributaries. Most reduced estimations of aggregate firmness were recorded in storm period.

Value of pH ranges from 7 to 8 and most abnormal amount of Mg was recorded during winter while least fixation was recorded amid rainstorm season. Greatest centralization of disintegrated Fe was recorded amid storm period and greater than the allowable limit for crisp water.

Open sewage and mechanical waste contain natural materials that are decomposable, need a lot of oxygen for oxidation process by smaller living beings and causes exhaustion of DO. In amphibian frameworks, outrageous natural and inorganic contribution from mechanical and city discarded diminish the obtainability of DO. Urban waste diminishes DO level and increase BOD and COD level in stream water. Abnormal state of BOD and COD might be because of the arrival of high volume of crude waste into tributaries. The high amount of TDS is connected with waste from day-to-day human activities. Pb

concentration was higher then allowed range at some points and lower at other collection points.

The levels of Mg-increased from upper to lower regions. The reason for Mg is anthropogenic activities. More elevated amount of free Fe, Pb and Cd in storm when water discharge was high. Presently expanded grouping of colloidal iron and lead masses amid high stream, likely because of resuspension of iron colloids built up onto bed residue.

Moreover, all these results indicate that the samples collected from upstream i.e., P1 had lesser concentration of contaminants as compared to those samples collected from downstream locations i.e. P5. This trend indicates that Nullah collected these contaminants from anthropogenic activities of inhabitants of Sialkot. These anthropogenic activities added contaminants into these nullahs thereby leading towards significant spatial variations of contaminants.

The comparative results of all the parameters indicated that R1 had higher mean as compared with the R2. This is because during the month of June, in which R1 samples were collected, there was less rain thereby the contaminants had higher concentrations. During the month of September there was higher flooding of Nullah Palkhu due to monsoon rains. The contaminants were therefore found in relatively diluted form. This indicated significant temporal variations of contaminants in Nullah Palkhu (Fig. 3).

Similarly, One-way ANOVA indicates the significant co-relation between different values. In current study, results indicate that EC, Cl and Total Hardness are highly significant which are less than 0.05 whereas other parameters as TDS, pH, Turbidity, NO_3^- , Ca, Mg, Salinity, BOD, COD, DO, Fe, Pb and Cd indicates there is no significant co-relation (Table 2).

Figure 3: Comparative mean of various parameters for spatio-temporal variations in the water quality of nullah Palkhu (R1: First reading, R2: Second reading).

4. Discussion:

Different studies show that human actions have profound impact on spatial and transient varieties in streams (DeCarlo *et al.*, 2005; Sullivan &

Drever, 2001). Comparable outcomes were acquired (Tsai *et al.*, 2003). Most extreme release was seen in rainstorm period and least release level was seen during winter and pre-storm periods (Sullivan &

Drever, 2001; Khan *et al.*, 2003; PCRWR, 2004; Singh *et al.*, 2005a; Qadir *et al.*, 2008).

The results of the present study regarding the values of TDS, EC and Cl are in accord with the findings of Qadir *et al.* (2008). It was also found that the TDS and EC calculated before monsoon were higher than that of after monsoon. Similar results were also found by Qadir *et al.* (2008) who found significant variations of TDS and EC during pre-monsoon and post-monsoon. The results of TDS and EC of present study are significantly higher than that of Nullah Hali (Qadir *et al.*, 2008). The presence of salinity, turbidity and hardness in water highly influences the accessibility of metals. The outcomes demonstrated that estimations of saltiness and hardness are similar to the results recorded by Qadir *et al.* (2008). In the clear water the concentration of the Ca was 0.06-210 mg/L (Nanda, 2005). PCRWR (2004) detailed mean convergence of Ca (30mg/L) in water tests assembled. The estimation of calcium as evaluated by the present investigation is markedly higher as contrast with the mean calcium estimation of PCRWR (2004).

The convergence of Mg was recorded in introduce consider was generally equivalent to River Chenab 12.0 mg/L (PCRWR, 2004). Taboada-Castro *et al.* (2002) additionally revealed greatest broke up Fe content while tributary was most extreme. The presence of Fe in broke down form can be because of its remobilization from earth surface in streams. Fe concentration computed in ebb and flow was greater to those in River Indus and lower to those of Ravi and Gomti streams (Singh *et al.*, 2004). The level of TDS was high; it is similar to the observations of Khan *et al.* (2003), where they studied TDS of Hudiarra drain and river Ravi. Pb that deposits on soil surface due to paints, burning car fumes and industrial processes can be a source of Pb in water bodies (Sutherland *et al.*, 2003; Tomazelli, 2003).

The concentration of Cd was also recorded higher than the normal for drinking water as clarified by USEPA (1990; 1993), CEC (1978) and WHO (1993; 2005). Elevated levels of Cd- in fresh water can be the results of anthropogenic activities of erosion of sediments that contain Cd (Jonsson *et al.*, 2002).

5. Conclusion:

Current study offers important information about spatial and temporal differences in water quality of Nullah Palkhu, Northeast of Pakistan which is a tributary of River Chenab. The results highlight that the increased concentration of TDS, EC, Cl, BOD, COD, DO, NO₃⁻, Fe, Pb, Cd, Ca, Mg, Salinity, Turbidity and Total Hardness in the Nullah is a result of human interventions. The loading of Nullah due to agricultural, domestic and especially industrial waste

has led to increased contamination of the Nullah. The water quality of the Nullah has deteriorated to such an extent that most of the aquatic life forms are disappearing from the Nullah. Political and administrative actions are important to implement of National Environmental Quality Standards and water quality regulations. Moreover, rules ought to be implemented for efficient disposal of domestic, agricultural and industrial wastes for the preservation of water quality and biotic heterogeneity of the Nullah.

Acknowledgements:

The research work for this paper is part of the second author's MPhil thesis.

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